

Linguistic acculturation preferences of Catalan local students towards their peers of Moroccan descent. The determining factors of linguistic assimilationism

Ursula Hinostroza-Castillo*^a Maria-Adelina Ianos^a, Cristina Petreñas^a and Cecilio Lapresta-Rey^b

^a *Department of Psychology, University of Lleida, Lleida, Spain;*

^b *Department of Geography and Sociology, University of Lleida, Lleida, Spain*

* Ursula Hinostroza-Castillo (Corresponding Author)

ORCID iD: 0000-0001-9282-4012

Department of Psychology, University of Lleida

Avinguda Estudi General 4, 25001, Lleida, Spain

ursula.hinostroza@udl.cat

Maria-Adelina Ianos: ORCID iD: 0000-0003-4953-3230

Cristina Petreñas: ORCID iD: 0000-0001-8083-2154

Cecilio Lapresta-Rey: ORCID iD: 0000-0002-3411-7077

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Linguistic acculturation preferences of Catalan local students towards their peers of Moroccan descent. The determining factors of linguistic assimilationism

As a response to the migratory movements initiated at the end of the past century in Catalonia (Spain), its educational system aims to promote interculturality and multilingualism as a way to achieve social cohesion. For this purpose, it is important to improve our understanding of the linguistic acculturation preferences endorsed by local students towards students of immigrant origin – a scarcely studied factor. The present study applied 349 questionnaires to analyze the determining factors and linguistic acculturation preferences of local high-school students regarding the linguistic acculturation profiles of their peers of Moroccan descent in Lleida (Catalonia, Spain). The main results showed that, in order of frequency, assimilation to Catalan, assimilation to Spanish-Catalan and multilingual were the three linguistic preferences endorsed by local students. The multinomial logistic regression model found the following determining factors: attitudes towards minority languages, attitudes towards multilingualism, Spanish self-identification, Spanish use with teachers and Catalan use with classmates. These results highlight the importance and need to further promote the use and embracement of minority languages in school settings as a possible way to increase the construction of multilingual preferences and deconstruct prejudices and stereotypes to ultimately achieve social cohesion.

Keywords: linguistic acculturation, multilingual education, Catalonia (Spain)

Introduction

Spain's linguistic diversity has gone through different stages of repression and revitalization. Franco's dictatorship (1939 – 1975) was one of the largest periods of linguistic repression in Spain and it was only with the Constitution of 1978 that Spain's multilingual reality was acknowledged and promoted. To democratize Spain and decentralize the power, the 1978 Constitution divided and granted autonomy to 17 regions of Spain known as Autonomous Communities. Additionally, article 3 of said Constitution, opened the possibility to recognize other languages. This is how, Catalan became the official language of Catalonia, Valencia and The Balearic Islands; Basque became the official language of the Basque Country, and Galician the official language of Galicia. The recognition of these languages as well as the autonomy given to each region led to bilingual education systems which promoted their regional languages and the use of Spanish (Taylor, 2022).

Globalization and large-scale migration flows shaped and posed new challenges to the Spanish educational system. Among its main challenges and goals was to ensure social cohesion and equal opportunities among students of immigrant origin¹ and local students, through an intercultural education which embraces language and cultural diversity (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2018). These aspects are especially relevant for the educational system of Catalonia, as it is a bilingual community, with Spanish and Catalan as official languages, which has adapted its linguistic and educational policy

¹ Students of immigrant origin is used to refer to students who, regardless of where they were born or their citizenship, have a background that is culturally different from the majority. It is important to clarify that the Spanish citizenship is not acquired directly by birth.

towards a multilingual education whose main aim is to achieve social cohesion and upward social mobility (Departament d'ensenyament, 2018).

To achieve these goals, it is necessary to understand the linguistic acculturation processes of all students. Understanding these processes entails recognizing the interplay between the acculturation strategies of students of immigrant origin and the preferences of locals (Piontkowski et al. 2000; Sáenz- Hernández et al. 2020; Yağmur & van de Vijver, 2012). Hence, the importance of promoting multilingual preferences in local students that recognize and value the cultural and linguistic background of their immigrant peers (Lapresta-Rey et al., 2021; Petreñas et al., 2021; Sáenz- Hernández et al., 2020). These preferences will help to achieve an intercultural education system and will help to reduce discrimination levels and possible conflict situations caused by the mismatch between local students' acculturation preferences and immigrant students' acculturation profiles. As a consequence, immigrant students' strategies will be strongly shaped by what local students prefer.

In this regard, previous studies have identified that acculturation preferences in general and linguistic ones in particular, are influenced by a variety of factors including variables related to multiculturalism and multilingualism, such as attitudes towards cultural diversity and immigration, attitudes towards multilingualism, multicultural ideology, ethnic tolerance, and attitudes towards minority languages (Richardson, op den Buijs, & Van der Zee, 2011; Van Osch & Breugelmans, 2012), and also factors related to ethnolinguistic identification (Montaruli et al., 2011a; Montaruli et al., 2011b).

Besides these factors, another major aspect which shapes linguistic acculturation preferences of the majority group is the valuation members of the majority group assign

to members of each minority group. The valuation differs according to minority group and is shaped by different aspects such as cultural closeness, religion, language, and cultural values (Montreuil & Bourhis, 2001). In the Spanish context, Moroccans are depicted as a devalued group in comparison to other minority groups, such as Latin Americans who are highly valued due to their cultural ties and common language (Bobowik & Basabe, 2013; Briones et al., 2012) and Romanians who although are also a devalued group, are valued higher than immigrants from Maghreb (Briones et al., 2012). Moroccans have a high cultural distance from Spanish culture which ultimately hinders their social integration (Basabe & Bobowik, 2013). Research has proved that this devaluation also applies to the educational context (Lapresta-Rey, 2021; Lapresta-Rey, 2022). As a result of this low valuation, local students have tended to endorse assimilation preferences towards their Moroccan peers (Briones et al., 2011).

With this background and considering the importance of acculturation processes in the configuration of an intercultural and multilingual educational system, the main objective of this study is to explore preferences and attitudes endorsed by local students towards the linguistic acculturation profiles of their Moroccan peers. The influencing factors that shape these preferences will also be investigated. Based on the knowledge generated, a further aim of this analysis is to discuss its implications in the creation and consolidation of an educational system that enhances social cohesion.

Linguistic acculturation and education

Acculturation is understood as the phenomenon that takes place when individuals of different cultural groups come into first-hand contact (Redfield et al., 1936). The classic model of acculturation proposed by John Berry (1997), states that the acculturation profiles of minority groups are the product of combining two dimensions:

(1) maintenance of heritage² culture, (2) and adoption of host culture. From the possibilities of combining these two dimensions, four types of profiles on acculturation are obtained: assimilation, separation, integration, and marginalization.

Different authors claim the important role that language plays in acculturation processes by acknowledging that all acculturation processes are linguistic by nature as intergroup relations imply linguistic interactions (Noels & Clément, 1996). Linguistic interactions such as the acquisition of other languages require the adoption of new social representations and cultural elements of the other group (Rubinfeld et al. 2006). As Gardner (1969) states, learning a new language does not only entail learning new vocabulary but also includes acquiring symbolic elements of the ethnolinguistic community.

Highlighting the role of language on acculturation processes and following Berry's classic model, Bourhis (2001) proposed the Interactive Acculturation Model (IAM). This model considers languages as the carrier of culture and so it claims that the process of acculturation allows understanding the changes in linguistic behavior such as language shift and loss and linguistic integration. This model, as well as Berry's one, distinguishes between the linguistic acculturation strategies adopted by the minority group and the ones adopted by the majority group. From now on, linguistic acculturation profile will be understood as the strategy adopted by the minority group (i.e. students of immigrant origin), meanwhile the term linguistic acculturation preference will refer to the preferences endorsed by the majority group towards specific

² A heritage language is defined as a language spoken by the students' parents at home and crucially, it does not refer to a dominant language.

linguistic minority groups (i.e. locals' preferences endorsed towards students of immigrant origin) (Bourhis, 2001).

[Insert Figure 1 here]

Thus, the Bourhis model (2001) proposes a different set of typologies for each group. As shown in Figure 1, this model proposes the following typology to refer to the linguistic acculturation preferences endorsed by the majority group towards minority groups: (1) multilingual: high adoption of the host language as well as high linguistic maintenance of the heritage language, (2) assimilation: high linguistic adoption of the host society and relatively low linguistic maintenance of the heritage language, (3) segregation: low linguistic adoption of the host society language and high linguistic maintenance of the heritage language, (4) exclusion: low linguistic adoption of the host society as well as low linguistic conservation of the heritage culture, and (5) individualism: this preference is exclusive for this model and portrays the preference of identifying as individuals rather than part of the minority or majority group (Bourhis, 2001). This model also claims that the linguistic acculturation preferences of the majority group are influenced by the valuation endorsed towards the minority group. Majority members are more likely to adopt a multilingual preference with valued groups and more likely to endorse an assimilation, segregation or even marginalization preference with devalued groups (Briones et al., 2012; Montreuil & Bourhis, 2004; Piontkowski et al., 2000; Rojas et al., 2014).

Linguistic acculturation preferences are a shaping factor in society at large as well as in educational contexts. For children and youngsters, schools are one of the main contexts where acculturation dynamics take place. Consequently, school contexts and acculturation processes are interrelated (Schachner, 2019). The acculturation processes carried out within educational contexts seem to follow the characteristics of

acculturation processes within public domains, as previous research has found that locals, including students and teachers, endorse assimilation and to a lesser extent multicultural preferences towards immigrant students (Navas et al., 2005; Navas et al., 2007).

In this regard, several authors indicate that the orientation of reception policies (at both educational and linguistic level) is one of the factors that best explain the development of acculturation preferences endorsed by the majority group (Berry, 2001; Bourhis, 2001; Montreuil & Bourhis, 2004). In this regard, intercultural and multilingual schools that opt for linguistic and educational policies which embrace diversity, tend to promote the development of multilingual linguistic acculturation preferences; meanwhile, assimilationist policies tend to promote assimilation preferences. However, even if intercultural and multilingual educational policies are pursued, they do not fully guarantee the endorsement of multilingual acculturation preferences by the majority group. This phenomenon could be explained by two main factors. First, for an educational system to be truly intercultural and to value multilingualism, society at large must also be socially, economically, politically, linguistically, and culturally intercultural (Berry et al., 2006; Yağmur & van de Vijver, 2012).

Second, the lack of a truly intercultural society leads to a gap between multicultural educational policies and daily educational practices (Faas et al., 2014; Petreñas et al., 2021). This gap is rooted in misconceptions such as thinking that intercultural education should be only addressed to minority groups, or to educational centers with high levels of cultural and linguistic diversity. Likewise, another common misconception is to assume that any type of cultural contact leads to a real capitalization and valuation. This real valuation could only appear if some conditions are met,

including the fact that it involves the participation of all educational members and not only members of minority groups (Galyapina & Lebedeva, 2016; Petreñas et al., 2021).

As indicated above, despite previous research supporting the promotion of multilingual preferences, studies in Spain and other countries such as Belgium, Finland, Portugal or Denmark have found that students of immigrant origin may feel pressured by their teachers and local peers to assimilate. This pressure is caused by teachers who believe that assimilation will help students to achieve better educational and social outcomes, as well as is caused by local peers that show more social acceptance towards students with assimilation strategies (Briones et al., 2012; Van Praag et al., 2016, Schachner et al., 2006). Thus, the need to better understand the factors that shape the linguistic acculturation preferences endorsed by local students towards their peers of immigrant origin.

Determining factors of linguistic acculturation preferences

Previous studies not merely focused on linguistic acculturation processes but rather on general ones have found that acculturation preferences are shaped by a series of psychosocial variables (attitudes towards multilingualism, multiculturalism, and minority languages, language uses, language attitudes and identifications, etc.). In relation to multiculturalism, Van Osch and Breugelmans' (2012) study found that Dutch participants were more supportive of multiculturalism towards minority groups that were perceived as less different, less threatening, warmer, and more competent. Furthermore, a study carried out in the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania identified that perceived safety from the Ossetians towards Russians is linked to higher scores on multiculturalism, tolerance, and mutual integration (Galyapina & Lebedeva, 2016; Lebedeva & Tatarko, 2013). Nonetheless, equality by itself is not enough to promote multicultural attitudes. According to Berry (2017), it is necessary for both equality and diversity to be present,

as diversity without equality leads to separation or segregation preferences and equality without diversity may lead to assimilation profiles and preferences.

Additionally, studies have found that strong identification with a single ethnic group has been linked to less welcoming attitudes towards outgroups (Montaruli et al., 2011b). Thus, people with strong single ethnic identification have more likelihood to endorse assimilation, segregation, and exclusion preferences towards other cultural groups, meanwhile people with dual identification are more likely to endorse a multicultural preference (Montreuil & Bourhis, 2001).

Studies carried out in the Basque country have shown similar results when addressing ethnolinguistic identification. Three types of identities have been identified in this context: monolinguals which can be either Spanish identity or Basque identity and bilinguals- biculturals (Montaruli et al., 2011a). Differences were found depending on their ethnolinguistic identity. It was found a pattern of ingroup favoritism in all participants as well as it was identified that Basque identifiers tend to have more bicultural patterns than Spanish identifiers (Garcia et al., 2017). Moreover, it was also found that strong regional identifiers tend to have less welcoming acculturation preferences than bilinguals, and that Basque identifiers and Spanish identifiers have more problematic relationships among them while dual identifiers usually play the role of language brokers and promote multiculturalism (Montaruli et al. 2011b).

Similar results were found in Catalonia, where Saenz-Hernández et al. (2020) explored the linguistic acculturation preferences of local young people towards Moroccans and Romanians and found that bicultural identification was a predictor of multilingual profiles. Assimilation and separation scores were also relatively high, and the participants favored the language they identified with for assimilation. In general, there was no difference between the answers regarding Moroccans and Romanians

except for the fact that adopting a Catalan identity or bicultural identity predicted lower marginalization scores towards Moroccans.

At the same time, linguistic identification and language use have been proved to point towards the same direction, as the use of language, especially in public spaces works not only for communication, but also carries a symbolic function as it represents the presence and strength of this language within this society. In this setting, the presence of the in-group language contributes to a positive identification towards the ethnolinguistic group (Landry & Bourhis, 1997). Hence, it would be expected that natives with a high use of their in-group language have a high ethnolinguistic identification and hence more likelihood to endorse assimilation, segregation, and exclusion preferences towards other cultural groups (Montaruli et al., 2011a; Montaruli et al., 2011b).

Focusing on Catalonia, the last linguistic survey of 2018 showed that language use varies according to the individual's origin and its unequal distribution may play a role on language maintenance. Respectively, this survey found that Catalan is mostly spoken by the inhabitants born in Catalonia as 98.2% of them prefer to use it, meanwhile this percentage decreases to a 61.1 % in inhabitants born in other regions of Spain and drops to a 51% in the cases of foreign born (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2018a).

Studies focused on the language attitudes of members of the majority group towards minority languages are scarce (Lapresta et al., 2010; Lasagabaster & Huguët, 2007). Lapresta et al. (2010) study carried out with students in secondary education schools in Catalonia found out that native students' attitudes towards the minority languages of their peers are neutral or slightly positive. However, these attitudes are based on folkloric believes rather than on a real valuation. Nonetheless, the study of

Newman, Trenchs-Parera & Ng (2008) also carried out in Catalonia shows that the languages of immigrant students are symbolically valued by local students who developed a cosmopolitan ideology.

There are few studies centered on the majority group's attitudes towards multilingualism. In this regard, Kimber's (2014) study carried out in Japan with university students, found out that the majority of participants includes English in their understanding of multilingualism; pointing out that possibly the conceptualization of multilingualism includes majority languages rather than minority ones.

However, there is more evidence on attitudes towards multicultural ideology. Previous research on this topic has identified negative correlations with strong ingroup identification (van Osch & Breugelmans, 2012) and positive relationships between bicultural or multicultural identities and preferences as well as tolerance towards diversity and uncertainty (tolerance of ambiguity) (Dewaele & Wei, 2013; Huff et al., 2017). Despite these previous findings, literature on multilingual ideology and linguistic acculturation preferences is still scarce. The lack of research focused exclusively on linguistic acculturation preferences creates the need to delve into this topic which is the main aim of the present article.

Sociolinguistic and educational context of Catalonia

The Catalan context is particularly interesting for the field of linguistics due to its change from a bilingual to a multilingual society. As previously stated, the 1978 constitution enabled language revitalization throughout different Spanish regions. In the case of Catalonia, this process was boosted by the 1983 policy called *Normalització Lingüística* (Linguistic Normalization). Its main aim was to reverse the language shift and revitalize Catalan by promoting bilingualism in a context where Spanish and Catalan were two competing languages. Language revitalization took place through

mass media and the introduction of Catalan as the vehicular language of the educational system. Catalan was seen as a sign of social cohesion and at the same time bilingualism was promoted as a way to reduce potential ethnolinguistic conflict between groups (Newman & Trenchs-Parera, 2015).

It was from the first decade of the 21st century onwards that the socio-demographic reality of the Catalan population changed due to the arrival of a large number of immigrants. This has been translated into the educational system, which has gone from 4.36% of foreign students in 2003 to 12.26% in 2020 (IDESCAT 2020a, 2020b). As a result, classrooms' reality shifted from a Catalan-Spanish bilingualism to a multilingual reality. Nowadays, this cultural and linguistic diversity is reflected in the presence of students from more than 140 nationalities (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2021).

In the light of this reality, new educational policies were designed and implemented. The Plan for Language and Social Cohesion 2004 [Pla per a la Llengua i Cohesió Social], its revisions (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2007, 2009) and its current successor: Linguistic model of the educational System in Catalonia [Model lingüístic del Sistema Educatiu de Catalunya] (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2018b) have as the main objective to promote and consolidate social cohesion through intercultural education and using Catalan as the backbone of a multilingual educational model. These new policies build on the Linguistic Normalization policy by adding socializing elements which allows fostering multilingualism and social integration (Trenchs-Parera & Newman, 2015; Trenchs-Parera 2018 & Lapresta et al., 2016).

All the above is transferrable to Lleida, the Western province of Catalonia. Lleida is an ideal context to analyze the linguistic acculturation processes of students for two main reasons. Firstly, it is the Catalan province with the highest proportion of immigrants 21.4% (IDESCAT 2020c, 2020d); and secondly, its foreign resident

population (and hence, students of immigrant origin) is unequally distributed. More specifically, immigrants of African origin, mostly from Maghrebi countries have the highest presence (45.33%), distantly followed by citizens of other EU countries, predominantly Romanians (24.95 %), and immigrants from South American countries (12.65%) (IDESCAT, 2020e).

Objectives

The present study has two main objectives: first, to identify the linguistic acculturation preferences of local students towards their Moroccan peers, second, to identify which variables could predict the adoption of each linguistic acculturation preference.

Regarding the factors that determine linguistic acculturation preferences of local students, it was hypothesized that variables related to linguistic and cultural diversity, namely, linguistic use and identification, ethnic tolerance, attitudes towards multilingualism, and attitudes towards minority languages, may influence specific acculturation preferences.

Based on the results obtained, challenges of the current educational and linguistic policies in Catalonia will be discussed, as well as possible measures and interventions which could help improve and increase the creation of multilingual preferences, and ultimately social cohesion.

Methodology

Participants:

Participants were 349 local students (50.7% girls and 49.3 % boys, M age= 15.04, SD = 0.79) from six different secondary schools from the province of Lleida. To be categorized as local, the students and both of their parents had to be born in Catalonia.

Procedure:

First, the Department of Education of the Government of Catalonia was contacted to obtain the necessary authorizations. After obtaining the approval of the Department of Education and based on its information regarding immigration, six schools were contacted in order to request their interest and collaboration to establish a schedule for data collection.

Instruments

The instruments were implemented collectively by a group of researchers. Students completed the questionnaire during school hours in their classroom with two researchers who clarified questions or doubts. Researchers ensured that students did not confuse the languages to which each item was referring to. Additionally, teachers were not present during this process which took approximately 60 minutes. The questionnaire was designed respecting the ethical guidelines established within Spanish territory. Informed consents from all participants were retrieved; therefore, participation was voluntary, and the confidentiality and anonymity of each participant were guaranteed. According to National Spanish Law no ethical committee approval was needed for this type of data.

The following are the instruments used in this study:

Linguistic acculturation preferences towards Moroccans were measured using four Likert items ranging from 1 – never to 5 – always. The items are based on previous scales designed by Berry (2005), Bourhis et. al (2001), Navas et. al (2005, 2007), and Lapresta et al. (2021) and they referred to the level of maintenance of the heritage language of the minority group (Moroccans) and adoption of the host languages (Catalan and Spanish) in two contexts: with their teachers, and with their classmates.

Linguistic identifications with Spanish and Catalan language were measured by two items on a 5-point Likert scale relating to the following questions: “To what extent

do you identify with the Catalan language? And to what extent do you identify with the Spanish language?”

Use of Spanish and Catalan were assessed using a total of 4 items on a 5-point Likert scale which measured the frequency of use of each language in two different educational settings: use of the language with classmates and with teachers.

Ethnic tolerance assesses the acceptance and recognition of individuals or groups that are culturally different. The ethnic tolerance scale was adapted from the tolerance/prejudice scale of the Mutual Intercultural Relation in Plural Societies (MIRIPS) questionnaire by Berry (2017). This scale is composed of 6 items on a 5-point Likert scale and its coefficient of internal consistency is of 0.75.

Attitudes towards multilingualism was composed by ten items on a 5-point Likert scale which evaluate the perception, attitudes, and feelings towards learning and knowing two or more languages, (“It is important to know two or more languages”, “Speaking two or more languages makes it easier to find a job”, etc...). Its internal consistency is of 0.54.

Attitudes towards minority languages included five items of a 5-point Likert scale related to embracing the presence minority languages (“We should strive to further promote the use of languages other than Catalan and Spanish (Arabic, Romanian, Chinese, Fula, etc...)”) and other five items related to the lack of interest towards minority languages (“It is useless to learn another language other than Catalan or Spanish (Arabic, Romanian, Chinese, Fula, etc...) as I probably will never have to use it”). The Cronbach’s Alpha obtained for this scale is 0.74.

Statistical treatment:

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v.27). A k-means cluster analysis allowed to classify the linguistic acculturation preferences

according Bourhis (2011) typology. Moreover, a multinomial logistic regression was conducted to analyze the determining factors of the linguistic acculturation preferences. One-way ANOVAs analyses were conducted to support the results of the regression analyses.

Results

Linguistic acculturation preferences of local students towards their peers of Moroccan origin

Results from the cluster analysis indicated three linguistic acculturation preferences: assimilation to Catalan, assimilation to Catalan and Spanish, and multilingual (Table 1). Namely, 199 participants (46.71%) showed an assimilation to Catalan preference by giving low scores on the adoption of Spanish and the maintenance of the heritage language of their Moroccan peers but high scores on the adoption of Catalan. Meanwhile, 138 participants (32.39 %) endorsed an assimilation preference to Spanish-Catalan, as they reported high scores on the adoption of Catalan and Spanish, and low scores in the maintenance of the heritage language of their Moroccan peers. Finally, 89 participants (20.89 %) obtained high scores in all clustering variables, corresponding to a multilingual preference.

[Insert Table 1 here]

Psychosocial and linguistic variables by linguistic acculturation preferences

A series of one-way ANOVAs were conducted to analyze the differences between linguistic acculturation preferences with regard to the psychological and linguistic variables of interest (see Table 2). The ANOVAs indicated there were significant differences among groups in five variables: *Catalan use with teachers*, *Spanish use with*

teachers, Spanish self-identification, ethnic tolerance, attitudes towards multilingualism and attitudes towards minority languages. The Bonferroni post-hoc tests conducted to further explore these differences showed that participants who endorsed a multilingual preference *used Spanish with teachers* more frequently than participants who endorsed assimilation to Spanish and Catalan ($t = 2.59, p = .031, r = .14$) and those who endorsed assimilation to Catalan ($t = 3.29, p = .003, r = .18$). They also had stronger *Spanish self-identifications* than their peers who endorse assimilation to Spanish and Catalan ($t = 2.67, p = .024, r = .14$).

Furthermore, participants with assimilation to Spanish and Catalan preferences used *Catalan with teachers* more frequently than their peers with Catalan assimilation preferences ($t = -2.43, p = .046, r = .13$). Similarly, participants with a preference for assimilation to Spanish and Catalan had more favorable attitudes towards multilingualism than those with multilingual preferences ($t = 2.67, p = .024, r = .15$). Finally, participants who endorsed Catalan assimilation showed higher *ethnic tolerance* than the ones with assimilation to Spanish and Catalan preferences ($t = -3.09, p = .006, r = -.17$).

[Insert Table 2 here]

Determining factors of linguistic acculturation preferences

A multinomial logistic regression was carried out to assess which variables may be determining factors of the linguistic acculturation preferences of local students. The multilingual preference was used as the reference category. Table 5 displays the results of the regression model. The logistic regression model was significant ($\chi^2 = 67.96, p < .001$) and both the deviance statistic ($p = .458$) and the Pearson test indicate the model is a good fit of the data ($p = .274$).

The values of *R statistic* both for the Nagelkerke measure ($R^2 = .20$) as well as for the Cox and Snell measure ($R^2 = .22$) are relatively similar and positive, and they indicate relatively decent size-effects.

[Insert Table 3 here]

The results show that there are four variables that predict if a person is more likely to have an Assimilation to Catalan preference than a multilingual one: *Spanish use with teachers*, *Spanish self-identification*, *attitudes towards multilingualism*, and *attitudes towards minority languages*. Namely, for participants who endorsed an assimilation to Catalan preference, higher scores on *Spanish use with teachers*, *Self-identification with Spanish* and *attitudes towards minority languages* indicate more likelihood of endorsing a multilingual preference. Respectively the change in the odds is 1.72 for *Spanish use with teachers*, 1.33 for *Spanish self-identification* and 2.5 for *attitudes towards minority languages*. On the other hand, for participants with an assimilation to Catalan preference, as *attitudes towards multilingualism* increases by one unit, the change in the odds of endorsing a preference for assimilation to Catalan is 1.11.

Likewise, three variables also predict the likelihood of a participant endorsing an Assimilation to Spanish and Catalan preference over a multilingual one: *attitudes towards minority languages*, *Catalan use with classmates*, and *attitudes towards multilingualism*. As in for the first group, an increase in the *attitudes towards minority languages* increases the odds by 2.63 for endorsing a multilingual preference; the same effect that creates the variable *Catalan use with classmates* as higher scores on it increases the odds by 1.75 for endorsing a multilingual preference, meanwhile the variable *attitudes towards multilingualism* increases the odds by 1.18 for endorsing a preference for assimilation to Catalan-Spanish.

Discussion

Regarding linguistic acculturation preferences, three preferences were identified: assimilation to Catalan, assimilation to Spanish-Catalan and multilingual. A great proportion of the participants (74.3%) tend towards an assimilation preference, either to only Catalan or to both Spanish and Catalan, in comparison to the 25.7 % who favor a multilingual preference. This finding goes in line with studies on acculturation and linguistic acculturation preferences which claim that multicultural and multilingual preferences are usually adopted in valued groups (Bourhis, 2001), while assimilation is mostly endorsed in devalued groups such as is the case of Moroccans in Spain (Briones et al., 2012). However, one of the few studies focused on Catalan high-school students found that their linguistic acculturation preferences towards Moroccan and Romanian peers were predominantly multilingual, closely followed by assimilation and separation (Sáenz-Hernández et al., 2020). These differences may be due to the domain analyzed in each study. Sáenz-Hernández et al.'s (2020) analyzed general linguistic acculturation, while this study focuses on the educational domain. Thus, the type of acculturation area seems to be a deciding factor, in line with Navas et al.'s (2005) acculturation model, which claims that acculturation preferences differ according to the domain analyzed. As the educational context belongs to the public domain, it makes sense that assimilation preferences were adopted (Navas et al. 2005; 2007). Moreover, these preferences could have been influenced by the role played by Catalan within the educational system, as it is not only the language of instruction, but it is also linked to educational and professional success (Lapresta et al., 2021).

With respect to the determining factors, of the nine variables analyzed, five were found to significantly predict linguistic acculturation preferences: *Spanish use with teachers, Spanish self-identification, Catalan use with classmates, attitudes towards*

minority languages and attitudes towards multilingualism. The results show the relationship between language uses and self-identifications, as both *Spanish use with teachers* and *Spanish self-identification* increased the likelihood of endorsing a multilingual preference rather than an assimilation to Catalan preference. Using Spanish and self-identifying with it in the Catalan educational context, where it is used as the instruction language and its continuously reinforced by educational agents, could be understood as the use and embracement of both languages, hence the multilingual preference.

For the case of participants who have an assimilation to Spanish and Catalan preference it was found that *Catalan use with classmates*, increased the likelihood of endorsing a multilingual preference. In this case, self-identification does not play a role; nonetheless a similar effect where both languages are appreciated can be identified. As using Catalan when endorsing a preference for assimilation to Spanish and Catalan could be understood as the embracement of both languages. Furthermore, previous studies have found that supporting Catalan is interpreted as protecting threatened languages which leads to support other minority languages and thus the multilingual preference (Pujolar & González, 2013).

As expected, and in line with previous research (van Osch & Breugelmans, 2012), more positive *attitudes towards minority languages* increased the likelihood of endorsing a multilingual preference rather than any of the two assimilation preferences.

On the other hand, higher scores on *attitudes towards multilingualism* predicted assimilation preferences. Although at first glance it could seem odd that this variable increases the likelihood of endorsing an assimilation preference rather than a multilingual one, it is important to bear in mind that multilingualism entails using two

languages or more, indistinctly of which type of language it is (Baker, 1992). These results go in line with Kimber's (2014) study as it could be interpreted that participants who favor multilingualism do not necessarily support the use of minority languages, but rather favor the use of more than one language, indistinctly whether those languages are a minority or a majority language such as English.

Educational implications and recommendations

The results of the present study point out the need to continue working towards a truly multilingual educational model in which there is no gap between policies and educational practices. For this purpose, it is necessary to continue promoting and embracing the use of minority languages within the whole educational community. In this regard, the current programs and strategies included in the actual educational model should be reinforced. For instance, language courses of heritage languages should be extended to all educational centers; furthermore, they should be addressed as a transversal issue rather than as an isolated knowledge only applied within language courses. A way to do so is to expand the range of courses by offering more courses in terms of number, languages and levels offered (e.g. A1, A2, etc...). Moreover, it is key to continue raising awareness of the importance and utility of learning minority languages among teachers and students.

In parallel, the curriculum should be reviewed and updated. Specifically, one major change could be to adopt a culturally responsive teaching approach. This approach would allow to embrace and recognize heritage languages and cultures as well as design educational content and activities which deconstruct and reflect on stereotypes and discriminatory perceptions of culturally different students. To adopt this approach, curriculum changes are not enough, it is also essential to offer continuous training for teachers and members of the educational community. Thus, it is important to raise

awareness of the topic from early childhood and promote genuine intergroup contact among students and teachers. If done correctly, this contact will lead a genuine intercultural and multilingual education.

Finally, policies should also be improved in order to genuinely promote multilingual acculturation preferences. Based on our results, we consider that it is necessary to design and implement measures adjusted to the characteristics of each group. Since our results are focused on the preferences towards Moroccans, we find the need to further work and promote cultural enrichment towards minority groups, but especially towards devalued minority groups as Moroccans, aiming to deconstruct prejudices and discriminatory beliefs attached to this group.

Conclusions and limitations

This study helps broaden the literature on the understudied field of linguistic acculturation (Gaudet & Clément, 2009; Lapresta et al., 2019, 2020, 2021; Sáenz-Hernández et al., 2020; Petreñas et al., 2019) highlighting the importance of language in acculturation processes and, hence, the importance to review and adjust linguistic and educational policies according to it and the sociolinguistic context. In this regard, the results of the present study as well as its limitation suggest further work that could be developed within this field.

In regard to its limitations, a qualitative approach could complement the current results and extend it to all Catalan provinces in order to identify patterns and compare results. Specifically, qualitative studies could focus on analyzing the values, perceptions, and judgements linked to the acculturation preferences of local students. This analysis will help identify which educational measures and policies should be designed to reduce discrimination perceptions and which could help increase

multilingual and multicultural practices within daily life. Furthermore, as the valuation of the immigrant group plays an important role in the linguistic acculturation preferences endorsed by the locals, a comparison among Catalan provinces could help to broaden our understanding of the situation, as each one of them hosts different proportions of minority groups. A better and a wider understanding of the linguistic acculturation preferences of local students will help to develop more adequate and culturally sensitive policies to ensure a truly multilingual education.

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Figure 1. *Linguistic acculturation preferences' typology. Adapted from Bourhis (2001) and Berry (1997)*

Table 1. Means and standard deviations of maintenance of L1 and adoption of Catalan for assimilation and multilingual preferences.

Linguistic Maintenance /		Catalan		Catalan-Spanish		Multilingual	
Adoption		(n = 199)		(n = 138)		(n = 89)	
		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Maintenance of L1	Classroom	1.42	0.64	1.25	0.47	2.97	0.97
	Teachers	1.29	0.52	1.18	0.41	2.86	1.01
	Schoolyard	2.53	1.10	2.17	1.03	3.53	0.83
Adoption of Catalan	Classroom	3.89	1.06	4.55	0.66	3.85	0.90
	Teachers	3.85	1.05	4.51	0.60	3.92	0.81
	Schoolyard	3.04	1.16	3.83	1.01	3.24	0.99
Adoption of Spanish	Classroom	2.62	0.91	4.43	0.61	3.75	0.83
	Teachers	2.45	0.87	4.35	0.69	3.80	0.79
	Schoolyard	2.55	0.95	3.88	0.88	3.42	0.91

Table 3. *Multinomial Logistic regression model predicting the linguistic acculturation preferences (category reference: Multilingual preference)*

		<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Wald</i>	<i>p</i>	Odds Ratio	C.I. 95% for Odds Ratio	
							Lower	Upper
Assimilation to Catalan	Catalan use (teachers)	-0.43	0.24	3.25	.072	0.65	0.41	1.04
	Spanish use (teachers)	-0.54	0.18	9.18	.002	.583	0.41	0.83
	Catalan use (classmates)	-0.23	0.21	1.23	.268	0.79	0.53	1.20
	Spanish use (classmates)	-0.06	0.20	0.10	.747	0.94	0.64	1.37
	Catalan self-identification	-0.09	0.18	0.25	.617	0.91	0.64	1.31
	Spanish self-identification	-0.29	0.15	3.92	.048	0.75	0.57	1.00
	Ethnic tolerance	0.33	0.26	1.54	.215	1.38	0.83	2.31
	Attitudes towards multilingualism	0.10	0.04	5.36	.021	1.11	1.02	1.21
	Attitudes towards minority languages	-0.92	0.30	9.45	.002	0.40	0.22	0.72

